

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE POPULATION OF KASHKADARYA REGION

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Annotation: The article analyzes the demographic processes related to the settlement of the population in Kashkadarya region, including the current permanent population size and their distribution across urban and rural areas. It also examines the changes in birth and death rates compared to previous years, as well as the variations in the number of recorded marriages and divorces through statistical analysis.

Keywords: population distribution, permanent population size, population density, demographic capacity, birth rate, death rate, number of marriages, number of divorces.

СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

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Аннотация: В статье проводится статистический анализ демографических процессов, связанных с расселением населения Кашкадарьинской области, текущего постоянного числа населения и его распределения по городам и селам, изменений числа рождаемости и смертности в сравнении с предыдущими годами, а также изменений в количестве зарегистрированных браков и разводов.

Ключевые слова: расселение населения, постоянное число населения, плотность населения, демографическая ёмкость, число рождаемости, число смертности, число браков, число разводов.

QASHQADARYO VILOYATI AHOLISINING STATISTIK TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada Qashqadaryo viloyati aholi joylashuvi bilan bog‘liq hududning demografik jarayonlari, hozirgi vaqtdagi doimiy aholi soni va ularning shahar va qishloqlar bo‘yicha joylashuvi, viloyatdagi tug‘ilishlar va o‘limlar sonining oldingi yillarga nisbatan o‘zgarishi, qayd etilgan nikoh va ajralishlar sonining o‘zgarishi statistik tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: aholi joylashuvi, doimiy aholi soni, aholi zichligi, demografik sig‘im ,tug‘ilishlar soni, o‘limlar soni, nikohlar soni, ajralishlar soni.

INTRODUCTION

In studying the economic geography of a population, its location is fundamental. As we know, the distribution of the population is often closely related to the natural and economic potential of the region. This necessitates scientific research to determine how many people can live within specific areas, or more precisely, to establish the demographic capacity of the region (DCR). In

determining the demographic capacity of a country, land, water, and recreational resources are considered primary indicators.

In the Presidential Decree No. PF-60 on the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," the 33rd objective aims to increase regional economies by 1.4 to 1.6 times through the balanced development of regions. This includes the implementation of five-year regional programs developed for 14 areas at the district and city level. It also involves creating and executing a practical action plan for cities and districts with "unsatisfactory" indicators in the socio-economic development ranking.

Improving living conditions in urban areas requires further enhancement of urbanization policies. Measures should be taken to transform the cities of Samarkand and Namangan into "million-strong cities" in the future. The initial phases of construction in the New Andijan city, designed for a population of 450,000, should be completed and put into operation. The urbanization level in the Kashkadarya region should be raised to 50%. [1]

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The demographic processes related to the population distribution of Kashkadarya region, the current permanent population size and its distribution across urban and rural areas, the changes in birth and death rates compared to previous years, and the changes in the number of registered marriages and divorces have been statistically analyzed. Specifically, the economic and geographical aspects of Kashkadaryo region's development have been studied by scholars such as R. Khodiyev, Ye. Umurov, A. Roziyev, S. Saidkarimov, T. Egamberdiyev, Yu. Akhmadaliyev, A. Kholmiraev, and M. Fayzullayev. Additionally, foreign scholars who have conducted theoretical and methodological research on the economic and geographical aspects of Kashkadaryo region and carried out statistical analysis of service indicators, including I.G. Tyunen, K.I. Ivanov, V.G. Kryuchkov, K.I. Lapkin, A.M. Nosonov, and A.N. Rakitnikov, have contributed important insights in this regard, which are cited in their works.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the article, the research was conducted using decisions adopted by the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the sector, works of scholars, scientific research, and statistical indicators related to this field within our country. The analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, and comparative methods were employed as traditional approaches to study the topic.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The demographic capacity of a region is defined by its ability to accommodate a certain number of residents, taking into account all relevant factors. This capacity is determined by resources such as land, water, job opportunities, recreational areas, and improvements in the ecological situation. The quantitative indicator of this capacity can change over time. In other words, the demographic capacity indicates how many residents a region can support if the current conditions are maintained, reflecting its potential in this regard.

In some districts, the demographic capacity has become extremely strained, characterized not only by a relative overpopulation but also by an absolute surplus of residents. Indeed, in such areas, the high population density, combined with insufficient access to land, water, and job opportunities, exacerbates social issues, leading to various negative consequences and putting pressure on the region.[2]

(Table 1).

The Population of Urban and Rural Areas by Districts of Kashkadarya Region

(As of the beginning of 2024; thousand people)

Indicators	Total population	Including:			
		Urban population	The ratio of total population %	Rural population	The ratio of total population %
Kashkadarya region	3560,6	1524,1	42,8	2036,5	57,2
Karshi	295,6	295,6	100,0	0,0	0,0
Shakhrisabz	147,2	147,2	100,0	0,0	0,0
<i>Districts:</i>					
Guzor	222,2	52,3	23,5	169,9	76,5
Dehqonobod	159,5	30,4	19,1	129,1	80,9
Qamashi	293,1	69,7	23,8	223,4	76,2
Karshi d	272,1	98,6	36,2	173,5	63,8
Koson	312,1	164,0	52,5	148,1	47,5
Kitob	282,0	105,1	37,3	176,9	62,7
Mirishkor	129,6	48,8	37,7	80,8	62,3
Muborak	93,4	74,3	79,6	19,1	20,4
Nishon	166,6	100,1	60,1	66,5	39,9
Kasbi	213,0	82,3	38,6	130,7	61,4
Ko'kdala	188,7	29,7	15,7	159,0	84,3
Chiroqchi	267,9	77,1	28,8	190,8	71,2
Shakhrisabz t d	235,1	56,7	24,1	178,4	75,9
Yakkabog	282,5	92,2	32,6	190,3	67,4

The location of the population causes a sharp deterioration of the ecological condition due to anthropogenic factors. In such conditions, the sanitary and

hygienic situation becomes complex, and the possibility of the spread of infectious diseases is high. The population distribution or its territorial composition is also characterized by the division into urban and rural areas. In developed countries, the majority of the population lives in cities, while in developing countries, rural populations predominate. In the Kashkadarya region, 57.2% of the population lives in rural areas. This makes the development of rural infrastructure, culture, industry, and transportation an urgent issue. From this perspective, the social and economic development of rural areas is a priority direction of the regional state policy. (Table 1).

Until the second half of the 20th century, the relatively low socio-economic living standards in Uzbekistan led to high mortality rates among the population. Although the birth rate was high, the population grew very slowly. From the second half of the 20th century onwards, mortality rates in Uzbekistan decreased slightly, and life expectancy increased. As a result, there was growth in both the quantity and quality of the population.

As of January 1, 2024, the permanent population of Uzbekistan is 36.799 million people. In terms of regional distribution, the share of the permanent population of the Kashkadarya region is 9.7%. The permanent population of the region, as of January 1, 2024, is 3.5606 million people, which is an increase of 78.3 thousand people, or 2.2%, compared to the beginning of 2023.

As of January 1, 2024, the urban population of the region is 1.5242 million people (42.8% of the total population), while the rural population is 2.0364 million people (57.2%).

From January to December 2023, the number of births totaled 101,852, which represents an increase of 3,573 people, or 3.6%, compared to the same period in 2022. The birth rate coefficient was 28.9 per 1,000 people, which is a 0.4-per-mille increase compared to 2022. The growth in the birth rate was recorded in almost all areas of the region. The highest increases in this indicator were observed in Koson district, where the birth rate rose from 29.3 to 30.2 per 1,000, and in Nishon district, where it increased from 28.5 to 30.4 per 1,000.

In the period from January to December 2023, 101,900 children were born, with a birth rate of 28.9 per 1,000 people, which represents a 0.4-per-mille increase compared to the same period in 2022.

During the same period, 16,424 deaths were recorded, which is a decrease of 593 people, or 96.5%, compared to 2022. The death rate coefficient was 4.7 per

1,000 people.[3] A significant increase in mortality rates was observed in Dehqonobod (from 5.8 to 6.7 per 1,000) and Koson (from 3.7 to 4.8 per 1,000).

In 2023, 30,900 marriages were registered in the Civil Registry Offices, with a marriage coefficient of 8.8 per 1,000 people. During the same period, 3,400 divorces were recorded, with a divorce coefficient of 1.0 per 1,000 people.

The variability of the demographic capacity in a region expands as the productive forces develop, and the effectiveness of the impact of science and technology on nature and the economy increases. For example, in the Kashkadarya region, the economic and social conditions of a population of 508,000 people (in 1959) were much lower than the current population of 3,408,300 (in 2022). The demographic capacity of the region increased as a result of the development of new lands in the 1970s-1990s, the formation of irrigation and reclamation infrastructure, the discovery of underground resources, and the construction of processing industries. This expansion further increased with the independence of our republic, as the country began to develop and process its natural resource reserves to meet domestic needs. The demographic capacity of a region is conditionally determined and requires the development of productive forces in the state and its regions, together with ecological measures.[4]

The most important characteristic of population distribution is expressed through its density indicator. Density can be calculated in gross and net (pure) terms. The gross density refers to the total area of the country or district and shows how many people live per square kilometer. For example, the average population density in Uzbekistan is 78.6 people per square kilometer, while in the Kashkadarya region, this indicator is 119.1 people per square kilometer, placing it 9th in the country (as of 2022).

If this indicator is calculated based only on areas where people live, particularly irrigated lands, it is referred to as net or pure density. The density of cultivated land is usually of particular significance for the rural population.

There is a certain relationship between demographic density, the location of production, specialization, and territorial concentration, as well as economic density. These two indicators tend to develop in inverse proportionality. In other words, the fewer irrigated lands per capita, the higher the population density per unit of area.[7]

The total land area of the Kashkadarya region is 2,856.8 thousand hectares. This accounts for 6.4% of the total land area of the country, which is 44,892.4 thousand hectares. The largest land area is in Dehqonobod district (395.7 thousand

hectares), which is nearly the same as the land areas of Sirdaryo (427.6 thousand hectares) and Andijan (430.3 thousand hectares) regions. The districts of Mirishkor (312.5 thousand hectares), Muborak (307.0 thousand hectares), and Chiroqchi (283.7 thousand hectares) also have large land areas, and together, these districts account for 45.5% of the total land area of the region.

The irrigated lands in the Kashkadarya region cover 514.1 thousand hectares, which accounts for 11.9% of the total irrigated lands in the country (4,312.9 thousand hectares). This shows that while the region occupies 6.4% of the country's total land area, it holds 12% of the country's irrigated lands.

In terms of land area, Dehqonobod district ranks first in the region, but in terms of irrigated lands, it ranks last.

As of January 1, 2022, 64.0% of the irrigated lands in the region are located in flat areas, mainly in the Karshi Steppe, which has been developed for centuries, and in the districts that have been historically cultivated (Koson, Mirishkor, Kasbi, Karshi, Muborak). The population of the Kashkadarya region as of January 1, 2022, is 3,408.3 thousand people, which accounts for 9.7% of the country's total population.[8]

When analyzing the population density across the administrative districts of the region, the highest density is found in Kasbi (313.8), Karshi (285.0), and Yakkabog (246.3) districts, while the lowest density is observed in Muborak (29.4), Dehqonobod (38.2), and Mirishkor (38.6) districts.

The analysis shows that the highest population density is observed in areas where processing industries are developed, around urban centers, in regions with long-standing irrigation agriculture, and in agro-industrial districts (Kasbi, Karshi, Yakkabog). Naturally, such areas are characterized by an intensive development direction of production. At the same time, in regions with an extensive agricultural system, such as livestock farming, especially pasture-based livestock farming, and mining industry areas, population density is much lower (Muborak, Dehqonobod, Mirishkor). In these areas, natural conditions, terrain features, and altitude zones also have a significant impact.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in some districts, the demographic capacity is extremely strained, where not only is there a relatively large population, but also an absolute excess of people. Of course, in such areas, the extremely dense population, along with insufficient access to land, water, and employment opportunities, exacerbates social problems and leads to various negative consequences. The density of the

population in these areas contributes to the sharp deterioration of the region's ecological condition due to anthropogenic factors. Additionally, under such conditions, the sanitary and hygienic situation is often not satisfactory, and the potential for the spread of infectious diseases is greater.

Based on this indicator, the current utilization of land and water resources in the region allows for a demographic capacity that can accommodate nearly 5 million people. As mentioned above, this capacity is conditionally determined. With the implementation of scientific and technological advances in the use of the region's natural resources in economic sectors, this number is expected to increase. Additionally, by implementing measures such as locating raw material processing industries in smaller districts with higher demographic capacity, the region can achieve an ecologically sound population distribution.

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